

Nitrohydroxy Aromatic Ketones. Part II. Nitrohydroxy-acetophenones and -propiophenones

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Synthesis of nitrohydroxy-acetophenones and -propiophenones has been effected by nitration of hydroxyketones. Replacement of a halogen by a hydroxy group has also been used for the preparation of 4-hydroxy-5-nitroacetophenone.

In an earlier communication¹, synthesis of some nitrohydroxy-acetophenones by Fries migration and also by direct nitration of some hydroxyacetophenones has been described. In view of the fact that a nitro group hinders Fries migration of nitrophenyl esters and also direct acylation of nitrophenols, yields of the ketones obtained by these methods are generally unsatisfactory. It was therefore thought worthwhile to investigate further the suitable conditions for the synthesis of these compounds by direct nitration of hydroxyketones.

Hydroxyacetophenones and hydroxypropiophenones have been found to undergo nitration satisfactorily in presence of sulphuric acid (d 1.8) at -2° to 0° with a mixture of sulphuric acid (d 1.8) and nitric acid (d 1.52). Nitrohydroxy ketones, prepared by this method, have been described herein. Synthesis of 4-hydroxy-5-nitroacetophenone has also been effected by hydrolysis of 4-chloro-5-nitroacetophenone by heating with sodium acetate and acetamide.

The nitrohydroxy ketones obtained are crystalline solids, insoluble in water, soluble in common organic solvents, form coloured solutions with aqueous alkalis, and readily afford 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones.

EXPERIMENTAL

Hydroxyketones required for nitration were prepared by the Fries migration².

2-Hydroxy-3-nitro-5-methylpropiophenone.—A solution of 2-hydroxy-5-methylpropiophenone (5.5 g.) in H_2SO_4 (conc., 20 ml) was cooled to -2° and an ice-cold mixture of HNO_3 (d 1.52, 3 ml) and H_2SO_4 (d 1.8, 3 ml) was added dropwise with stirring during $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The temperature was maintained at -2° to 0° during the operation. The reaction mixture after keeping for 20 mins. was poured on ice, when the nitro-ketone separated. It was immediately filtered, washed well with water, and recrystallised from ethanol in pale needles (5.5 g.), m.p. 151° . (Found: N, 6.6. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{11}O_4$ N: N, 6.7%).

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1. Joshi and Singh, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **75**, 4993.

2. *Ber.*, 1908, **41**, 4271.

Nitration of other hydroxyketones was effected similarly. The nitrohydroxy aromatic ketones obtained are described in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	Hydroxyketone.	Hydroxynitro ketone.	Cryst. from.	M.P.*	Yield.	Formula.	Fund.	Reqd.
1	2-OH-5-chloro-A	2-OH-3-nitro-5-chloro-A.	MeOH	132°	80%	C ₈ H ₆ C ₄ NCl	Cl : 16.2%	16.5%
2	2-OH-5-bromo-A	2-OH-3-nitro-5-bromo-A	EtOH	99.5°	75	C ₈ H ₆ O ₄ NBr	Br: 30.3	30.8
3	4-OH-P	4-OH-5-nitro-P	„	67°	80	C ₉ H ₉ O ₄ N	C : 55.1 H : 4.6	55.4 4.6
4	2-OH-3-methyl-P	2-OH-5-nitro-3-methyl-P	„	113°	82	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₄ N	C : 57.0 H : 5.2	57.4 5.3
5	2-OH-5- „ -P	2-OH-3-nitro-5-methyl-P	„	151°	75	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₄ N	C: : 56.9 H : 5.1	57.4 5.3
6	4-OH-6- „ -P	4-OH-3-nitro-6-methyl-P	AcOH	92°	65	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₄ N	C : 57.1 H : 5.0	57.4 5.3
7	2-CH-5-chloro-P	2-OH-3-nitro-5-chloro-P	EtOH	98°	72	C ₉ H ₆ O ₄ NCl	Cl : 15.3	15.5
8	2-OH-5-bromo-P	2-OH-3-nitro-5-bromo-P	„	101°	73	C ₉ H ₆ O ₄ NBr	Br : 28.9	29.2

*All melting points given are uncorrected
N.B. A and P denote respectively acetophenone and propiophenone.

2-Hydroxy-5-nitroacetophenone.—An intimate mixture of 2-chloro-5-nitroacetophenone (10.0 g.), sodium acetate (15.0 g.) and acetamide (15.0 g.) was heated on a sand bath at 180–200° for 2 hours. It was then cooled and poured into water. The mixture was treated with NaOH and filtered. The filtrate on acidification provided 2-hydroxy-5-nitroacetophenone (4.5 g.) which on recrystallisation from ethanol melted at 99.5°. Mixed m.p. of the sample obtained by the Fries migration showed no depression. (Found: N, 7.5. Calc. for C₈H₇O₄N: N, 7.5%).

2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazones.—A solution of 2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in ethanol containing a few drops of H₂SO₄ (conc.) was refluxed on a water bath with an equimolecular quantity of the ketone solution in ethanol. The 2,4-DNP separating was filtered, washed well with water and ethanol, and recrystallised from ethyl acetate. Yields in all cases were almost quantitative. The 2,4-DNPs are described in Table II.

TABLE II

Sl. No.	Colour.	M.P.*	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
1	Yellow	228°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₇ N ₂ Cl	17.6	17.7
2	„	239°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₇ N ₂ Br	15.8	15.9
3	Saffron yellow	226°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₇ N ₂	18.5	18.6
4	Yellow	245°	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₇ N ₂	17.9	18.0
5	Orange	234°	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₇ N ₂	17.9	18.0
6	Yellow	241°	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₇ N ₂	17.8	18.0
7	Reddish yellow	230°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₇ N ₂ Cl	17.0	17.1
8	Yellow	238°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₇ N ₂ Br	15.2	15.4

*All melting points given are uncorrected

**Sl. number corresponds to compounds in Table I.